

Using the Web as a Corpus for Extracting Abbreviations in the Serbian Language

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Abstract

In this paper we discuss the results of extracting abbreviations in the Serbian language by using the web as a corpus. The results are compared to those retrieved by using the standard corpus of contemporary Serbian language. Using the web as a corpus is a very recent trend. It is a valuable source of data for research in computational linguistics and information extraction. Still, there are no adequate tools for searching the web, which are geared to linguistic needs. We chose crawling as a process for collecting data from the web, in order to extract abbreviations in the Serbian language. We show that, by using the web as a corpus, a higher number of abbreviations can be found and they are more recent.

Introduction

In the last decade, methods that are being used in computational linguistics research have drastically changed. Fifteen years ago, most research was focused on selected examples of sentences. Today, it is common to use huge corpora of text for research purposes.

One of the greatest advantages of corpus-based research is that corpora provide a way to discover facts about the language which are not observable or quantifiable by manual means. However, corpus-based research has some disadvantages:

- the design and creation of text corpora can be expensive;
- corpora are fixed at a point in time;
- corpora do not provide access to up-to-date information on language use or the changes which are occurring.

In an attempt to overcome these disadvantages, a lot of language scientists and technologists are increasingly turning to the web as a source of language data.

The web contains a lot of text resources, more than any known corpus. It is the only available source for some languages. It is free and instantly available.

In this paper, we will discuss these advantages, as well as when is the use of the web as a corpus a better alternative. We will show on the sample task of extracting abbreviations in the Serbian language that using the web as a data resource leads to better results than using a relatively large corpus.

The World Wide Web

The World Wide Web is a marvelous place, with a vast range of languages, content domains and media formats. The Web is constantly changing and growing, and even the best estimates can only approximate its extent and

composition. The most reliable estimates suggest that the number of publicly indexable web pages in mid-2005 is in the range of 10 to 20 billion.

This is only the visible part of web. Far larger is the “invisible” Web, the information that is on the web, but cannot be accessed through search engines – these are documents or data that reside in databases and can be explored only by entering relevant queries in a form. There are a number of researchers who are trying to improve search engines and to pull out such data (a “deep web” concept), but this concept is still at the initial phase of development.

In addition to the web being a huge collection of text data, linguists have one more benefit from web which lies in its multilingualism. Data from Global Reach (2004) show the following percentages of users for the top ten languages: English 35.2%, Chinese 13.7%, Japanese 8.4%, Spanish 9.0%, German 6.9%, French 4.2%, Korean 3.9%, Italian 3.8%, Portuguese 3.1%, Dutch 1.7%, other 10.1%.

Another advantage of the web as a corpus is that, for some languages, the web is the only source of data.

Why Use the Web as a Corpus?

Different kinds of data are needed for different linguistic purposes. For many research questions, data from a standard corpus like the British National Corpus or the Corpus of Contemporary Serbian Language are sufficient. But there are cases in which the data needed to answer or explore a question cannot be found in a standard corpus. It could be because the phenomenon under consideration is rare, belongs to a genre or register not represented in the corpus, or stems from a time that the corpus data do not cover (for example, it is too new). In these cases the Web is a good and convenient source of data, because of some of its properties:

- Freshness and spontaneity: the content of compiled corpora ages quickly, while texts on contemporary is-

sues and authentic examples of current, non-standard, or emerging language usage resides on the web;

- Completeness and scope: existing corpora may lack a text genre or content domain of interest, or else may not provide sufficient examples of an expression or construction easily located online;
- Linguistic diversity: languages and language varieties for which no corpora have been compiled are found online;
- Cost and convenience: the web is virtually free, and desktop computers to retrieve and process web pages are available to researchers and students alike.

Computational Linguistics Approach

Using the web as a corpus is a very recent trend. The number of approaches that are relevant to Computational Linguistics is still rather small. But already the web has been tried for tasks on various linguistic levels: lexicography, syntax, semantics and translation.

Lexicography: Lexicographers find WWW as an interesting and very rich source for discovering and classifying new lexical material from the wealth of texts in the web. This includes finding and classifying new words or expressions and gathering additional information such as typical collocations, subcategorization requirements, or definitions. Jacquemin and Bush (2000) describe an approach of learning and classifying proper names from the web. This is a worthwhile undertaking since proper names are an open word class with new names being continually invented. Later in this paper we will describe an approach for finding new abbreviations in the Serbian language and their definitions from the web.

Syntax: Martin Volk (2002) discussed how the vast textual resources of the web can be exploited to improve parsing. He used frequencies obtained from search engines to resolve PP (prepositional phrase) attachment ambiguities (see also Volk 2000 and Volk 2001). An English sentence consisting of the sequence verb + NP + PP is a priori ambiguous. The PP in example sentence 1 is a noun attribute and needs to be attached to the noun, but the PP in 2 is an adverbial and thus part of the verb phrase:

- (1) *Peter reads a book about computers.*
- (2) *Peter reads a book in the subway.*

If the subcategorization requirements of the verb or of the competing noun are known, the ambiguity can sometimes be resolved. But often there are no clear requirements. Therefore, there has been a growing interest in using statistical methods that reflect attachment tendencies. For example for sentence 1 the triple frequencies for (*read, about, computer*) and (*book, about, computer*) are needed as well as the unigram frequencies for *read* and *book*. Obviously it is very difficult to obtain reliable frequency counts for such triples. Therefore the largest corpus available, the WWW, is used. With the help of a WWW search engine, frequency values ('number of pages found') are obtained and used to compute co-occurrence values, based on the following formula (X can be either the verb V or the head noun N1):

$$\text{cooc}(X,P,N2) = \text{freq}(X,P,N2) / \text{freq}(X)$$

For example, if some noun N1 occurs 100 times in a corpus and this noun co-occurs with the PP (defined by P and N2) 20 times, then the co-occurrence value $\text{cooc}(N1,P,N2)$ will be $20 / 100 = 0.2$. The value $\text{cooc}(V,P,N2)$ is computed in the same way. The PP attachment decision is then based on the higher co-occurrence value.

Semantics: Retrieving semantic information from the web is a very difficult task, but also the most significant one with regard to practical applications. Agirre et al. (2000) describe an approach to enriching the WordNet ontology using the WWW. The authors show that it is possible to automatically create lists of words that are topically related to a WordNet concept. If a word has multiple senses in WordNet, it will be accompanied by synonyms and other related words for every sense. Agirre et al. query the web for documents exemplifying every sense by using these co-words. The query is composed by using the disjunction of the word in question and its co-words and by the exclusion of all co-words of the competing senses (via the NOT operator). The documents thus retrieved are locally processed and searched for terms that appear more frequently than expected using the X2 function. The resulting topic signatures (lists of related words) are evaluated by successfully employing them in word sense disambiguation. Moreover, the authors use the topic signatures to cluster word senses. For example, they were able to determine that some WordNet senses of *boy* are closer to each other than others. Their method could be used to reduce WordNet senses to a desired grain size.

Translation: The web is a very useful tool for looking up how a certain word or phrase is used. Queries to standard search engines allow for restrictions to a particular language or to a particular country. Therefore, it has become easy to obtain usage information. Grefenstette (1999) has shown that WWW frequencies can be used to find the correct translation of German compounds if the possible translations of their parts are known.

Also, there are a lot of translations that exist and are published in the web. The task is to find these text pairs, judge their translation quality, download and align them, and store them into a translation memory. Furthermore, parallel texts can be used for statistical machine translation. Resnik (1999) developed a method to automatically find parallel texts in the web.

Diachronic change: The web may also be used to observe language change over time and to provide access to today's language. Volk (2002) showed on example of two recent words in Swiss German, *Natel* and *Handy*, which are competing for prominence in Switzerland, how the web can be used to determine the language changes. He proved his hypothesis that *Handy* has become more frequently used, by checking the frequency of occurrence on the web before and after January 1st, 2000. He used the Hotbot search engine since it allows this kind of time span search.

Later in this paper, we will show how the web can be used to find out new abbreviations in the Serbian language, and potentially their definitions. This is something that can not be done by exploring a standard corpus, because of the nature of that class of words. For example, for a long time in every newspapers article in Serbia it

was common to use the word Kosovo for the Serbian province called Kosovo i Metohija (Kosovo and Metohija). But very recently, this trend has changed and almost every journalist started to use abbreviation KiM instead. This word can not be found in a standard corpus of the Serbian language, and therefore the web as a corpus is the only solution.

Information extraction approach

Information Extraction (IE) is the next step up from search engines in fulfilling information processing needs. It is a technology that is futuristic from the user's point of view in the current information-driven world. Rather than indicating which documents need to be read by a user, IE systems analyze unrestricted text in order to extract information about pre-specified types of events, entities or relationships. These facts are then usually entered automatically into a database, which may then be used to analyze the data for trends, to give a natural language summary, or simply to serve for on-line access. Links between the extracted information and the original documents are maintained to allow the user to reference context.

IE is closely related to Computational Linguistics, because it uses a lot of CL and NLP techniques and methods. Question Answering, perhaps better than any other area, represents this tight connection between these areas.

Depending on what data needs to be extracted, researchers could choose a standard corpus or the web as a source of data. For many purposes, a standard corpus can be a good place to search for facts. But also, there are a lot of facts that could not be found in corpora, maybe because they are too new or because a standard corpus does not cover the topic. For example, information about upcoming conferences is something that could be found only on WWW. If a user queries a standard search engine with “*conference CL 2006*”, s/he will get a list of sites that contain those words, and then will have to download these pages, read them one by one to find out what is the date or the place where the conference will be held. But, he doesn't need all the other information he will get by the way. IE systems provide a way to get just the information user needs (the name, the place and the date of the conference) and a possibility to maybe sort that results by date, something that standard search engines can't do.

One good example of an IE system is Froogle (<http://froogle.google.com>). It is a search engine which, as a result, has a list of products available online, with pictures, prices, descriptions and links to particular product.

Accessing and Collecting Data from the Web

Currently, data on the web can be accessed only through search engines. The problem is that search engines are not tuned to the needs of linguists. For example, it is not possible to query for documents that contain the English word *back* as a noun. Thus, linguists have to find out other techniques for their research based on web data.

In principle, there are several options for using data from the web.

Searching the whole Web through a commercial engine directly

Researcher can use a commercial engine, for example Google or AltaVista, directly. Although those search engines are not adapted to the needs of linguists, some research can be done just by using them. There are many examples in the literature where researchers used frequencies returned by search engine to determine some facts about language (see Volk 2002).

Using frequency data from a search engine (“Google frequencies”) can be useful, but is also problematic. For one thing, all search engines perform some sort of normalization: searches are usually insensitive to capitalization (“*jasna*” and “*Jasna*” return the same number of matches; the first is an adjective in the Serbian language, the second is a proper name), automatically recognize variants (“*white-space*” finds *white space*, *white-space* and *whitespace*) and implement stemming for certain languages (as in *lawyer fees* vs. *lawyer's fees* vs. *lawyers' fees*). While such features can be helpful when searching information on the web, they may also distort the frequency counts. It is possible to deactivate some, but not all of these normalizations. However, this requires a detailed knowledge of the query syntax, which may change whenever Google decides to update its software. Another serious problem is duplicate texts found by search engines; the same text can be present in several different web pages (citation of someone's speech, for example). Such duplication, which is much more common on the Web than in a carefully compiled corpus, may inflate frequency counts drastically. Manual checking could in principle be used to correct the frequency counts, both for normalization and for duplication, but it is prohibitively time-consuming (since the original Web pages have to be downloaded).

Adding pre- and/or post-processing to the search engine, to refine query results

Using the features of a search engine is a good idea, but not enough for the majority of linguistic researches. There are several examples of systems that pre-process queries before they are sent to search engines and post-process the results to make them more linguist-friendly. Probably the most famous pre-/post-processing systems are WebCorp (Kehoe & Renouf, 2002) and KWicFinder (Fletcher 2001).

WebCorp is a Web-based interface to search engines such as Google and AltaVista, where the user can specify a query using a syntax that is more powerful and linguistically oriented than the one of the search engines. For example, it is possible to use wildcards such as * meaning “any substring” (as in: “*ing”). Moreover, WebCorp organizes the results returned by the search engine in a clean “keyword in context” format, similar to that of standard concordance programs.

However, ultimately these tools are interfaces to Google and other search engines, and as such they are subject to all the query limitations that the engines impose, they cannot provide information that is not present in the data returned by the engines, and they are subject to constant brittleness, as the nature of the services provided by the engines may change at any time.

Collecting pages from the Web (randomly or controlled) and searching them locally

Except for very small corpora, the process of downloading web pages to build the corpus (and any post-processing that is applied) must be automated. In principle, this is the optimal approach to using the Web as a corpus, given that it provides full control over the data. However, crawling, post-processing, annotating and indexing a sizeable portion of the Web is by no means a trivial task. Even though the idea of building a linguist search engine has been around for at least 4 years, to this date the only projects that have produced concrete results involved (relatively) small-scale crawling. For example, Ghani et al. (2001) described how to build corpora of minority languages by sending queries to the search engine using words “typical” of specific languages. Baroni and Bernardini (2004) used a similar approach to create specialized language corpora for terminographical work. Baroni and Kilgarrieff (2006) have developed very large corpora from the Web for German and Italian languages by crawling the web and post processing retrieved pages (*DeWac* and *ItWac*). For generating seed URL’s, they used results retrieved by Google search engine which was queried with randomly chose pairs of words. The crawling process and post processing of downloaded pages will be described later in this paper.

Exploring Abbreviations in the Serbian Language

Using the web as a corpus turned out to be the best alternative for analyzing named entities. Proper names, for example, are an open word class with new names being continually invented. Standard corpora can not serve as a data source, since they don’t contain newly added names. A similar class of words is abbreviations.

In our research we try to collect acronyms, as one type of abbreviations in the Serbian language, together with their possible definitions. The task was to find newly acronyms, Available corpus of contemporary Serbian language (SrpKor), developed at Faculty of Mathematics, University of Belgrade, is made of different resources, such as books and news articles and it consists of 23,532,367 tokens. Newspaper texts date from 1993, textbooks and monographs date from 1980, while literature part dates from 1920 and it consists of both original and translated works. The most recent text in SrpKor dates from year 2000. Therefore, in order to find acronyms that are recent, we have to use some other resource. The web was the only adequate, because of its freshness and availability. Nevertheless, we did our research on the SrpKor as well, in order to compare the results.

Abbreviations in the Serbian language are often written with all letters in upper case. For example, very common abbreviations in Serbian language are:

SCG – Srbija i Crna Gora (Serbia and Montenegro)

SFRJ – Socijalistička federativna republika Jugoslavija (Socialistic federal republic of Yugoslavia)

BIA – Bezbednosno informativna agencija (Agency for state security and information)

SANU – Srpska akademija nauka i umetnosti (Serbian academy of science and art)

NBS – Narodna banka Srbije (National bank of Serbia)

But there are also cases like *BiH* (Bosnia and Hertze-govina) or *KiM* (Kosovo and Metohia). So, in order to find abbreviations, we searched for words not longer then n letters (5 in our case), where more than half of the letters are upper case. We also excluded from the results words that satisfy the above condition and whose context is all written in upper case. Considering there is no search engine or tool which supports this kind of queries, we automatically collected web pages by crawling the web in order to get data for our research.

Crawling the web

A crawler is a program that traverses the web by following hyperlinks from one page to another. It usually starts from a predefined list of seed URLs. The set of URLs used to initialize the crawl and various parameter settings of the crawler (e.g., the number of pages to be downloaded from each domain) has a strong impact on the nature of the corpus being built.

Broad crawl of the Web requires considerable memory and disk storage resources. So crawling the whole or large part of web for linguistic purposes maybe is not such a good idea. Instead, we carefully choose seed URLs for the crawling process, having in mind our task to pull out recent acronyms. For that purpose, we put as seeds the URLs of daily newspapers from Serbia.

Post processing

After the crawling process had finished and pages were downloaded, the next step was to eliminate HTML content – tags, scripts and other “non Serbian” text. Web corpus, attained in the described way, contained about 500,000 words. The remaining text was then tokenized. Words, together with their context and source, were put into the database.

Exploring abbreviations

Once we had words stored into the database, the search could start. We extracted words not longer than five letters, with more than half letters in upper case, where the other words in the context are not written in upper case. We also searched the standard corpus of contemporary Serbian language with the same query and joined results. When this process was finished, we had around 600 different acronyms. The results are shown in Table 1.

Percentage of abbreviations that appeared in both corpora	9%
Percentage of abbreviations that appeared only on web	33%
Percentage of abbreviations that appeared only in standard corpus	57%

Table 1. Percentage of found abbreviations

Among the results, there were strings that do not represent abbreviations, like Roman numbers (*XIV*). Also, because of the five letters limit, some abbreviations are not recog-

nized (*UNESCO*). But we assumed that percentage of wrong words that are recognized as abbreviations or that are not recognized at all is the same in both standard corpus and web, so we compared the results.

Of the union of the abbreviations found through both sources (web and the corpus of contemporary Serbian language) 9% represent abbreviations was present in both sources. Among the acronyms found on the web 33% were not found in the SrpKor, although the size of text collected from web was 50 times smaller than SrpKor. Those were the acronyms we were looking for, acronyms that are new and recent, and therefore they can not be found in SrpKor. On the other hand, among all acronyms found in the corpus of contemporary Serbian language 57% were not found on the web. The reason for the later is that many of the abbreviations in the standard corpus represent organizations, political parties or countries that no longer exist (SSSR, for example). This is not surprising, having in mind that we used URLs of daily newspapers in Serbia as a seed for crawling. The articles that can be found there are mostly about recent events and they don't contain historical texts. By extending the seed URLs for crawling, the percentage of abbreviations that appear only on web, and not in standard corpus, can only grow. Therefore, this is a kind of research that can not be done without using the web as corpus.

Conclusion

In this paper we have discussed at length the advantages and disadvantages of using the web as a data resource for research in computational linguistics. We considered the task of identifying recent acronyms in the Serbian language using the corpus of contemporary Serbian language and the web as data sources. We were able to find more abbreviations and more recent ones on the web. We argue that further linguistic research would benefit greatly from automated tools that can leverage the wealth of information found on the web to perform similar tasks that we programmed in our system.

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